

Automatic Control of Class Weights in the Semantic Segmentation of Corrosion Compounds on Archaeological Artefacts

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Abstract. The semantic segmentation for irregularly and not uniformly disposed patterns becomes even more difficult when the occurrence of categories is imbalanced within the images. One example is represented by heavily corroded artefacts in archaeological digs. The current study therefore proposes a weighted loss function within a deep learning architecture for semantic segmentation of corrosion compounds from microscopy images of archaeological objects, where the values for the class weights are generated via genetic algorithms. The fitness evaluation of individuals is the estimation that a surrogate of the deep learner gives concerning the segmentation accuracy. The obtained class weight values are compared to a random search through the space of potential configurations and another automated means to compute them, in terms of resulting model accuracy.

Keywords: semantic segmentation, deep learning, class imbalance, weighting, evolutionary algorithms, surrogate models, archaeology

1 Introduction

Semantic segmentation is one computer vision task with numerous applications in the computational decision support for complex and sensitive fields. While the detection of human and animal beings, as well as general objects, from natural images, has reached outstanding performance, the delineation of more ambiguously formed shapes still poses a problem to the deep learning (DL) algorithms. Moreover, a second issue comes with the shortage of data available

for analysis in practical scenarios. This leads to the situation when, while some classes that have to be distinguished are well represented in the data set, the others have very few examples from which the algorithm can learn the pattern.

The class imbalance problem is frequent in general in the classification process and a weighting procedure in the loss function is commonly employed to address it, either in a manual or in an automatic fashion. The open source machine learning libraries also offer in-built tools for an automatic calibration of class weights, based on standard formulas. However, these are general and thus not always able to capture entirely the particularities of the task at hand.

Under these circumstances, the current paper aims to introduce an automatic method to optimally adjust the class weighting by means of evolutionary algorithms (EA). However, since the repeated training of the DL model in order to evaluate every resulting potential solution would be highly resource-consuming, the behaviour of the deep architecture shall be simulated through a surrogate cheaper machine learning model. Surrogate-based optimization [13] has proven to be an efficient procedure, with various machine learning approaches offering a partial model of the original expensive phenomenon. Its use for hyperparameter tuning of DL models has also been exploited with success [3], [12], [18], [21].

The real-world instance on which the surrogate-based class weighting will be performed comes from archaeology and envisages the intricate task of recognizing and delineating the corrosion compounds on recently excavated artefacts before proper restoration. Such objects are very old and therefore highly degraded from the long time contact with the soil and related components (temperature, water, minerals, salts, organisms), as well as from the sudden interaction with O_2 once excavated. The shape of the corrosion exhibition is thus irregular and variable, and necessitates a careful, laborious examination.

DL offers the possibility for the segmentation of corrosion compounds and a first inspection was made in [19]. There are 5 categories associated with this corrosion recognition task (4 compounds plus the clean metal). Nevertheless, the complexity of the shapes makes the semantic segmentation task difficult and a good detection accuracy is not possible for all the classes. Moreover, the issue grows significant due to the imbalance in the distribution of the classes.

The paper is structured as follows. A look at the related state of the art is provided in section 2. Section 3 introduces the data set with the occurrence of each corrosion compound and the proposed method, together with the experimental setup. The results are discussed in section 4. The conclusions and future directions are given in section 5.

2 State of the Art

The detection of corrosion by means of DL can be in a first instance modeled through an easier, rougher classification formulation [15], [16]. For the more complex semantic segmentation task, the reference DL architectures of U-Net and Mask R-CNN [8] are employed as standard models. The problems usually come from civil engineering, where the presence of rust has to be effectively

acknowledged on the resistance structures [6], [8]. In the field of archaeology and cultural heritage preservation, the first attempt to segment the diverse corrosion products, specific to each material type of object manufacture, had been reached in [19] through a U-Net architecture. Nevertheless, it had been observed that the model focused on accurately detecting the clean metal part, which was larger defined and present in all images, and little emphasis was put on the corrosion products that were scarcer and more difficult to detect.

Hyperparameter optimization within DL is another issue connected to the present research. A proper tuning of the involved variables is directly related to the performance of the model. Various strategies based on heuristics have been proposed, ranging from the now already classical EA [10] to the newest entries of swarm intelligence [2]. Although the interest in the current work lies in the adjacent weighting of the classes, the problem is similar to that of DL parameter calibration: better chosen weights will lead to improved performance, and it all should be achieved within efficient computational restrictions. As pointed out in the introduction, surrogate-based optimization is ideal for such constraints.

The class imbalance problem has been a subject of interest in research works. Multi-class imbalance [4] is even more complicated, as there is a hierarchy of inequality [20]. The solutions come up at the data level and at the algorithmic stage. Sampling techniques are used for data driven changes, while the algorithmic modifications include cost targeted penalization, threshold adjustment for prediction probabilities and ensemble learning [4], [20].

Literature examples where EA were used for class imbalance problems refer their usage at the algorithmic level to generate near balanced bags in bagging ensemble methods [14] and their application at the data level for generating synthetic examples for the minority class taking into account the distribution measure [1]. In the current paper, the optimal weight values are generated by an EA individual and included in the loss function of the U-Net.

3 Data and Methodology

The data, the methodological design and setup are described in the following.

3.1 Data

The current case scenario considers degraded artefacts made of copper. They are the property of the Oltenia Museum, Craiova, Romania. The task will be to spot 4 types of compounds on the microscopy image of their surface: two resulting from the corrosion in the presence of O_2 , i.e. CuO (black color) and Cu_2O (red tone), and two other products caused by the interaction of the artefact with water and salts, i.e. $(CuOH)_2CO_3$ and $CuCl$ (green appearance). Additionally, a fifth category will be represented by the clean part of the object, where there is only raw Cu . A sample image is depicted in Fig. 1(a), with the manual annotations of the corresponding corrosion products given by labelled polygons, and performed with the support of the VGG Image Annotator tool [5].

Fig. 1. (a) An example of a copper artefact under the microscope and the corrosion compounds observable on its surface. The dark brown delineations (9, 10) are $CuCl$, the light brown (1, 3, 5, 6, 12, 13) represent Cu_2O , the blue ones (2, 7, 8, 11) denote CuO and the green markings (4, 14) are $(CuOH)_2CO_3$. (b) The top plot shows in percentages how many of the images in the training, validation and test sets contain pixels of each class. The bottom plot indicates the average coverage (%) over the entire image; this is computed considering for each class only the images where it occurs.

The images are split between training, validation and test sets as 131, 21 and 22, respectively. The images in the training set come from 20 objects, while the ones from the validation and test sets come from 4 and 3 distinct objects, respectively. Naturally, the separation of objects (and of the images accordingly) between the three sets assures there are no items appearing in any two sets at the same time.

Fig. 1(b) illustrates the class occurrence in the training, validation and test sets. The top plot indicates that it is only clear Cu that appears in all the images, while the least represented component, both with respect to the number of images where it appears, but also as concerns the coverage area, is $CuCl$. The plots in Fig. 1(b) need to be analyzed only together, because the values of the bars from the second plot are calculated only for the percentage of images that are shown in the top plot for each corresponding class, i.e. only for the images that contain that corrosion compound. Accordingly, for instance, the CuO regions for validation and test sets in the second plot are 1.8% and 1.1% respectively, but in fact, the former is computed as an average from 47.6% of the pictures in validation (only these images contain such CuO pixels), while the 1.1% computed in the test set is computed from 95.5% of the test images.

It is therefore unarguably a very unbalanced pattern recognition task that demands a reconsideration of the learning within the model. Specifically, an EA will explore the search space of weight values for the different classes of the problem. The fitness evaluation will be powered by the estimation given by a

surrogate model instead of running the convolutional model with the exploratory weights, in order to save computational time.

3.2 Design and Setup

The methodology involves several concepts that will be first briefly defined. The class weights are involved in the expression of the DL loss function, in order to balance the segmentation categories, and thus constitute important variables, whose values influence the accuracy of the model. Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) will be used to generate an initial random sample of values for the class weight parameters. Traditional regression models can be used in place of more expensive computational simulations (such as DL runs in this case) within the heuristic-based optimization of parameters, i.e. what is referred to as surrogate-based optimization. Among the nature-driven optimization techniques, EA are already a classical and reliable option. The heuristic will be employed to generate optimal configurations for the class weight parameters. The surrogates previously trained on the segmentation accuracy of initial LHS samples can further act on behalf of the DL technique, in evaluating these potential new variable values.

The flow of the proposed procedure is given in Fig 2. The set of LHS configurations offers a random sweep over the space of values for the weights (Step 1). Each configuration is given to the DL model as the class weighting to be included in the loss function and the returning accuracy is appended as an output to the LHS samples (Step 2). A surrogate model is then assigned to this formed data set in order to learn the correspondence between LHS weight values and DL segmentation accuracy (Step 3). The surrogate will then be used as the fitness function when evaluating new individuals generated by an EA (Step 4).

Fig. 2. The steps of proposed design.

There are 100 LHS configurations that are designed for the 5 weights that are controlling the categories of the classification problem: Cu , $CuCl$, $(CuOH)_2CO_3$, CuO and Cu_2O . The intervals for them are established as $[0, 2]$ for Cu and $[5, 30]$ for the Cu corrosion compounds. The intervals are inspired by the values calculated using the methodology in [9] and implemented under *scikit-learn* [11], which for this data set were equal to 0.21, 24.21, 8.9, 14.27 and 16.04, corresponding to the classes enunciated above. The values are computed based on

the distributions of the samples (by samples it is referred to all the pixels in the images) to the classes from the training data. Through the LHS, a larger exploration of the search space is allowed.

The image pixel accuracy is employed for training the U-Net model that is utilized for the semantic segmentation task. The accuracy results reported will be calculated class-wise, due to the large imbalance in the occurrence of the corrosion labels. As Fig. 1(b) shows, all images contain pixels with *Cu* (or background, as we refer it interchangeably), but not all images contain the other compound classes. Thus, the pixel accuracy for each class in turn (ratio of correctly identified pixels of the class to total pixels of the class) is calculated and this value is averaged over the number of images corresponding to the label. Consequently, we will have a separate classification accuracy for each compound over the specific data set, be that validation or test. The final classification accuracy will be the average of the ones obtained for each class, including *Cu*.

There are thus 100 U-Net models that are trained using the different LHS configurations. The results from the validation set serve as reference points for the regression models that will be further used as surrogates. Three regression models are trained using all 100 LHS configurations and the validation DL output, in order to replace the more expensive model in evaluating new possible weight values. The three were chosen to be conceptually different, i.e. linear regression (LR), support vector machines regression (SVR) and random forests (RF). Each of them is further separately used as a fitness evaluation function for a genetic algorithm (GA) that explores the search landscape of the weights looking for a better value for fitness that should ideally correspond to the actual application of the U-Net model on the validation set.

The implementation of the GA uses the PyGAD library [7]. The same GA setup is used for each of the 3 surrogate models. An individual encodes the 5 weights for the classes with similar starting intervals as they are used for generating the LHS configurations. The GA setup options used are further detailed: the population size consisting of 10 individuals, 20 generations of evolution, tournament selection, single-point crossover and a mutation probability of 0.2. The latter corresponds to changing one gene per individual. There are 10 different runs completed for each of the 3 GA. When it comes to the evaluation of a newly obtained GA configuration, its accuracy value estimated by a surrogate regression model is attributed as the individual fitness.

4 Results and Discussion

This section presents the resulting outcomes, whose insights are further discussed. A comparison is made between those obtained for the class weights computed via the open source *scikit-learn* library (following the methodology derived from [9]) versus those when using LHS and surrogate-based optimization.

Fig. 3 illustrates the connection between the generated LHS configurations and the validation accuracy that is obtained when these weights are used for training the U-Net models. The data is split into 3 intervals for each component

for producing the box plots from Fig. 3. The *small* samples contain all LHS samples that have the values in $[0, 0.67)$ for Cu and $[5, 13.33)$ for the other classes, *medium* represents LHS with values for Cu in $[0.67, 1.33)$ and $[13.33, 21.67)$ for the others, and the highest rest of the configurations are in *large*.

Fig. 4 illustrates the way the LHS samples are modeled by the 3 regression approaches in (a) and the feature importance given by the RF model in (b). Fig. 4 (c) and (d) illustrate the histogram values of the GA genes and helps in understanding where the search is concentrated within the population (10 individuals) over the 20 generations of evolution.

Figures 5 and 6 provide various insights into the GA weight results obtained in the surrogate simulation, versus their success in the real DL application and also as compared to pre-calculated values as in [9]. All 4 plots in Figure 5 show the results obtained by applying the U-Net using the best solutions discovered by the 10 repetitions of the GA using the 3 different regression models (SVR, LR and RF). The (a) plot shows side-by-side the outputs of the surrogate models (as they were embedded in the GA fitness function) and the actual results given by the U-Net when including the weights discovered by the GA using the 3 surrogates. The (b) plot depicts the DL validation accuracy for each corrosion class in turn from the configurations determined by the 10 GA runs.

Fig. 6 (a) and (b) show through the box plots the weights that led to the top 10 results with respect to the validation accuracy. Additionally, the best weight configuration of the LHS, as well as of the regression (in particular, the SVR model led to the best DL accuracy on the validation set), are illustrated. Moreover, the calculated weights according to [9] are also pointed out in the graphic. The latter obviously appears in the same regions both in the LHS and regression sides in the plot. (c) and (d) show a comparison in DL results for validation and test sets. The dotted red lines indicate the result of the configuration with the computed weights following [9]. Out of the 10 best results determined by the weights found through GA and regression models, half are discovered by the SVR model, 3 by LR and 2 by RF. The results on the test set are obtained by applying the best configurations from validation.

Further, we discuss in detail the content of the resulting plots. Fig. 3(a) does not only show how the 100 values are generated for each component in turn, but also indicates how the values are interconnected. Additionally, the colors express the quality of the validation accuracy when each specific setup is used. The weight of the Cu is the one that has a striking importance: the lines that depart from the smaller values of the parameter are particularly red, while towards the middle (between 0.5 and 1.5) the colors of the lines are closer to yellow and finally, going to the top, they are green. The other components do not have such a clear determination of the colors for the lines in any region. However, at a thorough analysis, it can be observed that lower values are discouraged for $CuCl$ and CuO , as there are fewer red lines at the bottom of the interval for them. The observations are also confirmed by the plots on the second row of the figure. As (b) illustrates, *small* values for Cu lead to the best overall accuracy result. On the contrary, as (c) exhibits, Cu *small* weights lead to the worst results for

Fig. 3. (a) The connections between the 100 LHS configurations; the color corresponds to the accuracy. Box plots with intervals for class weights split into small, medium and large: (b) overall classification accuracy, (c) only Cu (background) accuracy.

its class. This can be explained by the fact that the smaller weights values for Cu lead to a worse classification accuracy for Cu but, on the other hand, the quality of results improves for the other classes and thus the overall accuracy, which is computed as the mean over the classification accuracy of all classes (see subsection 3.2), is enhanced. Smaller values for CuCl and CuO indeed lead to a poorer overall accuracy ((b) and (a)).

The (a) plot from Fig. 4 is calculated from the 100 LHS configurations representing only the weight of Cu , as this is shown to be the most influential by the charts in Fig. 3. In fact, the RF model reveals that undoubtedly the Cu weights are the most important with respect to the validation accuracy (Fig. 4(b)).

The bottom of Fig. 4 shows the histograms for the 5 genes of the GA, for the entire population (c) and for the best solution (d). As noted in subsection 3.2, the GA has a population of 10 individuals and runs for 20 iterations. The first row shows that the GA explores even beyond the initial intervals that are used for the initialization, i.e. gene 0 (Cu) and gene 2 ($(\text{CuOH})_2\text{CO}_3$). While values of almost 10 were also present in the population for the former (with the initialization in $[0, 2]$), values close to 0 were also explored for the latter (while the gene values were initialized in $[5, 30]$). However, the best individual (d) always had the values within the intervals considered for initialization.

Fig. 5 illustrates various angles of the collected outputs. It can be observed from (a) that the SVR model proves to be *pessimistic*, meaning that the ap-

Fig. 4. (a) The training data with only the Cu weight and the accuracy, along with the solutions obtained from RF, SVR and LR. (b) The weight importance determined by RF. Histograms of the GA genes, obtained from all generations in one run when the fitness was given by SVR, for the entire population (c) and for the best solution (d). Genes 0 - 4 correspond to the weights for Cu , $CuCl$, $(CuOH)_2CO_3$, CuO and Cu_2O .

Fig. 5. Obtained results using the 3 different surrogate models. (a) The overall accuracy estimated from the surrogate vs the real DL outputs from the same inputs. (b) Box plots with the actual DL results per each class. The strip plots at the bottom show the real DL accuracy for each class on the validation (c) and test (d) sets.

Fig. 6. Box plots with the weights that led to the top 10 validation results for the compounds (a) and *Cu* (b) during LHS and all surrogate models (dots indicate the best). DL results of the top 10 values for the validation set (c) and when applied to the test set (d). Pre-calculated weights as in [9] are also plotted by dots and red line.

proximations of the model are below the actual outputs of the U-Net when using the weights discovered by the GA-SVR surrogate. On the contrary, RF is *optimistic*, as its results are above the actual U-Net values. LR has the results well interpolated with the actual values. While in (b) the GA-SVR surrogate has one very poor result for *Cu* (of 9.8%), there are 5 results when no pixels were identified at all for class $(CuOH)_2CO_3$, when using the weights given by the GA-RF surrogate. When checking the reason why this happens, it is observed that all these are cases when the weight for $(CuOH)_2CO_3$ is between 0.02 and 0.2. Thus, there are some runs in which gene 2 of the GA is very close to 0. In Fig. 4(d) the best results did not correspond to such a case, but that was for only one run and for SVR as a surrogate. What is more, there is also one outlier for which LR has a poor value for $(CuOH)_2CO_3$ and that happens as well for a low weight of that class, i.e. 0.2. The second row from Fig. 5 shows similar types of plots for the U-Net accuracy on the validation (c) and test (d) images, departing from the weights obtained in the 10 GA runs. Unfortunately, the test set has fewer images with any pixels of *CuCl* and, in the ones where present, the areas were even smaller than for validation and a lot less than in training. Thus, the results for this class were rather weak in the test set for all configurations.

While the average on the validation set between the top 10 results given by LHS and surrogates-driven search in Fig. 6 are almost identical (73.22% and 73.18%, respectively), the median favors the surrogate regression (72.24% vs. 73.64%). However, on the test set, the results unarguably favor the search through surrogates, as the averages are at 60.75% and 62.17%, respectively. At the same time, if the configuration that leads to the most accurate validation result that is discovered through the surrogate-based GA model is applied on the test set, the result is 65.26%. If the same is done for the best LHS setting as found

on the validation set, the test accuracy reaches only 62.73%. In comparison, the calculated weights through the approach in [9] lead to a test accuracy of 61.63%.

5 Conclusions

The paper discusses an appropriate class weighting for a semantic segmentation task where the pattern shapes are irregular and unbalanced. The best configuration is achieved by an EA backed by a surrogate regression model that gives the estimated accuracy of a DL with the loss function powered by the given values.

The results of the surrogate-based EA optimization (with SVR resulting as the best DL substitute) support the idea of evolving the optimal values for the class weighting in comparison to both a random LHS parameter search and the standard value of the *scikit-learn* package calculated for this purpose.

There are several directions for future work. The use of the Dice score as the segmentation metric could be a better alternative to handle class imbalance. The increase in the number of data images should also alleviate the issue. The consideration of an ensemble of surrogate models could also improve the performance. Also, relevant feature vectors for each compound could be extracted [17] and given to a standard neural network to view a parallel different processing.

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